

STUDY ON OCCUPATIONAL SAFETY PRACTICES AND HEALTH HAZARDS IN SELECTED INDUSTRIES IN ABIA STATE

Uka Kalu Ezinne¹, Obisike Victor Ugochukwu*¹ Okafor Anthony Ikechukwu², Ohaike, Rosemary Ekperemaka¹, Nwatu Maduka Solomon³

¹Department of Public Health, Abia State University.

²Department of Animal and Environmental Biology, Abia State University.

³Department of nursing Science , Abia State University.

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*Corresponding Author

Obisike Victor

Ugochukwu

Department of Public
Health, Abia State
University.

ABSTRACT

Occupational health and safety hazards remain critical concerns in industrial environments, particularly in sectors with physically and chemically intensive operations. This comparative study assessed health risks, hazard exposures, and safety measures practiced among workers in two industrial settings: a vegetable oil processing company and **Factory B** all in Abia State, Nigeria. The research aimed to evaluate the prevalence of physical, chemical, biological, and psychosocial hazards, examine the effectiveness of existing safety protocols, and explore the influence of organizational and individual factors on safety behavior. A cross-sectional descriptive design was employed. Data were collected through structured questionnaires administered to workers at the vegetable oil company and interviews with ten heads of units across five plants—Plastic, Carton, Lube,

PVC, and Noodles—at **Factory B**. descriptive statistics were used to analyze the data. Results from both sites revealed considerable exposure to occupational hazards. At the vegetable oil company, 75% of workers reported noise-related hazards and 68.3% noted heavy lifting. Chemical exposure was high (89.7%), with nearly half experiencing splashes, while 42.5% identified biological risks, particularly from waste disposal. Similarly, at **Factory B** 88% of respondents acknowledged chemical hazards, and 60% noted psychological stressors. Psychosocial factors such as long working hours and limited safety training also emerged as key contributors to safety risks in both settings. Safety practices varied across sites. While 71.4% of vegetable oil workers used personal protective equipment (PPE), waste

management and training were inadequate. At **Factory B**, 80% of plants had emergency plans, 90% had firefighting systems, and 60% had structured evacuation systems. Additionally, 60% observed organized safety services, and 64% confirmed the existence of safety committees. This study underscores the need for improved safety protocols, including regular training, enhanced emergency preparedness, medical surveillance, and comprehensive waste management. It recommends stronger regulatory enforcement and the integration of psychosocial and organizational considerations to ensure holistic occupational safety and health in industrial workplaces.

INTRODUCTION

Occupational safety and health (OSH) is vital for protecting workers from injuries, illnesses, and fatalities. Globally, over 2.93 million workers die annually due to work-related accidents and diseases, while an additional 395 million suffer from non-fatal occupational accidents and illnesses (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2023). These statistics highlight the profound human and economic burden posed by unsafe working conditions.

In developing countries like Nigeria, industrial workers are frequently exposed to hazards such as dust, noise, chemicals, and mechanical injuries due to poor safety practices and inadequate enforcement of safety regulations (Enwere *et al.*, 2023). In addition, many small and medium-scale industries operate without structured safety management systems. The Nigerian industrial sector—comprising manufacturing, construction, oil and gas, and agro-processing—has been particularly vulnerable to safety lapses. Workers often lack adequate personal protective equipment (PPE) and training (Abdulsalam *et al.*, 2024). For instance, a study in vibrated block industries revealed that although workers had basic knowledge of hazards, actual safety practices were poor (Abdulsalam *et al.*, 2024). OSHA (2023) stresses the need for hazard identification, worker participation, and management commitment in promoting workplace safety.

In Abia State, with its expanding industrial sector, there is limited research on occupational safety practices and associated health risks. Understanding the current safety practices and health hazards in these industries is crucial for developing effective interventions and policy reforms (Olatunji, 2018).

This study aims to assess occupational safety practices and health hazards among workers in selected industries in Abia State to support efforts toward safer and healthier workplaces.

This study, therefore, addresses the gap in monitoring and evaluating health and safety practices in manufacturing industries. By focusing on two contrasting industrial setups in Abia State, the research aims to provide insights into how safety protocols are implemented, the challenges faced, and the opportunities for improving worker protection and well-being.

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a cross-sectional descriptive survey design to assess occupational health and safety hazards among workers in two industrial environments in Abia State, Nigeria: a vegetable oil processing company and Factory B situated in Abia state. The cross-sectional approach was chosen to allow the researcher to collect data at a single point in time, enabling the comparison of different occupational settings regarding hazard exposure, safety practices, and worker perceptions. This design also facilitated the integration of both quantitative and qualitative data, ensuring a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter.

The study was carried out in two major industrial facilities. The vegetable oil processing company is involved in the processing and packaging of edible oil and is known for physically demanding operations that expose workers to various hazards. On the other hand, Factory B is a multi-sectoral industrial hub comprising five functional plants: Plastic, Carton, Lube, PVC, and Noodles. These plants are characterized by heavy machinery usage, chemical handling, and intricate production systems that make occupational safety a top concern.

The study population comprised workers engaged in operational, technical, and supervisory roles in both facilities. In the vegetable oil company, the population included factory-floor workers who were directly involved in processing, packaging, and materials handling. At **Factory B**, the population focused on unit heads and supervisors overseeing operations in the five plants.

A purposive sampling technique was used to select the two factories based on their industrial scale and exposure to occupational risks. For **Factory B**, a sample of ten heads of units—two from each of the five plants—was selected to represent the perspectives of approximately 50 employees. These individuals were chosen because they hold key positions and have direct insight into health and safety measures implemented within their respective plants.

Two main instruments were used for data collection. First, a structured questionnaire was administered to workers in the vegetable oil processing company. The questionnaire was divided into five sections covering demographic data, exposure to physical, chemical, and

biological hazards, usage of personal protective equipment (PPE), psychosocial factors such as long working hours and fatigue, and workers' perceptions of the effectiveness of current safety protocols. Secondly, a key informant interview (KII) guide was used to conduct interviews with unit heads and supervisors in **Factory B**. These interviews focused on areas such as the existence and functionality of safety committees, emergency preparedness, the availability of firefighting systems, the conduct of training and surveillance, and general organizational safety culture.

To ensure the validity and reliability of the instruments, the questionnaire and interview guide were reviewed by experts in occupational health, public health, and industrial safety for face and content validity. A pilot study involving 20 factory workers from a similar oil-processing facility was conducted to refine the questionnaire items. The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.81, indicating good internal consistency.

Data collection was carried out over a two-week period. The researcher conducted scheduled interviews with unit heads using the KII guide, ensuring privacy and confidentiality during the sessions.

Collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics with the aid of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25. Frequencies and percentages were computed to describe demographic characteristics, exposure to hazards, PPE usage, psychosocial influences, and perceptions of safety protocols. Qualitative responses from the interviews were transcribed, grouped thematically, and used to complement and triangulate the quantitative findings.

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from a recognized institutional ethics review committee. Participation was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents. They were assured of the confidentiality of their responses, and no identifying personal information was collected during the process.

RESULTS

Table 1: Health Safety Measures Practiced.

Item/Measure	Vegetable Oil Company	Factory B
Use of PPE	71.4% of workers used PPE	PPE usage implied through general compliance; not quantified
Emergency Plans	Not specified	80% of plants had emergency plans in place

Fire Safety Equipment	Not specified	90% had firefighting systems
Evacuation Systems	Not specified	60% had adequate evacuation systems
Organized Safety Services	Not reported	60% reported organized safety services
Existence of Safety Committees	Not reported	64% reported having safety committees
Waste Disposal Practice	68.3% of workers disposed waste in regular trash	Not explicitly stated

At the **Vegetable Oil Company**, 71.4% of workers reported the use of personal protective equipment (PPE), highlighting some level of compliance with basic safety standards. However, the factory lacked detailed records or structured emergency plans, organized safety services, or fire evacuation systems. Waste disposal was also poorly managed, with 68.3% of workers disposing waste in regular trash, indicating inadequate waste management systems. In contrast, **Factory B** exhibited a more robust safety infrastructure. Emergency plans were in place in 80% of plants, and 90% of units had functional firefighting systems. Evacuation systems were reported in 60% of plants, and 64% of respondents confirmed the presence of active safety committees. This suggests that **Factory B** is more organized in formalizing safety operations and emergency preparedness compared to the Vegetable Oil Company.

Table 2: Level of Knowledge of Occupational Health Hazards.

Knowledge Indicator	Vegetable Oil Company	Factory B
Awareness of Chemical Hazards	89.7% reported chemical exposure	88% acknowledged presence of chemical hazards
Biological Hazard Knowledge	42.5% reported biological hazards (especially from waste disposal)	Not explicitly quantified
Psychosocial Risk Awareness	68.9% reported long working hours as a risk	60% noted psychological hazards such as stress
Safety Training Availability	31.7% reported lack of continuous safety training	Training mentioned as inadequate

At the **Vegetable Oil Company**, 89.7% of respondents were aware of chemical hazards, particularly exposure from oil processing operations. However, only 42.5% recognized the risks associated with biological hazards, such as those from waste disposal. A notable 68.9% acknowledged the psychological toll of long working hours. Nevertheless, only 31.7% of workers reported having access to structured safety training, pointing to a major gap in continuous learning. At **Factory B**, knowledge levels were similarly high with 88% of respondents aware of chemical hazards and 60% identifying psychological risks like stress and mental fatigue. While biological hazards were not specifically measured, respondents frequently mentioned the need for better waste handling. Safety training was identified as inadequate, though there was an acknowledgment of its importance. This comparison

suggests that while awareness exists in both companies, **Factory B** places more emphasis on hazard education than the Vegetable Oil Company.

Table 3: Factors Affecting Safety Practices.

Factor	Vegetable Oil Company	Factory B
Long Working Hours	68.9% of workers affected	Fatigue due to long hours reported
Safety Training	31.7% reported lack of continuous training	Training programs inadequate
Monitoring and Review	Not specified	Emphasis placed on regular reviews and monitoring
Commitment to Safety	Not discussed in detail	Lacking commitment from both staff and management
Attitudes Toward Safety	Not assessed	Many workers were not committed to safety practices

Workers at the **Vegetable Oil Company** cited long working hours (68.9%) and inadequate safety training (31.7%) as the most significant factors affecting their adherence to safety protocols. Unfortunately, there was no institutional monitoring or review system in place, and commitment to safety practices by both management and workers was not clearly documented. Conversely, respondents at **Factory B** identified similar challenges, particularly fatigue from long shifts and insufficient training programs. However, there was a stronger emphasis on regular monitoring, supervisory roles, and periodic safety evaluations. Despite these structures, many workers indicated that both staff and management lacked consistent commitment to safety principles. This highlights a partial implementation of safety management systems that require further reinforcement.

Table 4: Types of Hazards Encountered.

Hazard Type	Vegetable Oil Company	Factory B
Physical Hazards	Noise (75%), Heavy lifting (68.3%)	Not quantified
Chemical Hazards	89.7% reported chemical exposure, 48.3% experienced splashes	88% acknowledged chemical hazards
Biological Hazards	42.5% linked to poor waste handling	Not detailed
Psychosocial Hazards	Long work hours, inadequate breaks	Stress, overwork noted by 60%
Fire Hazards	Not specified	90% firefighting systems in place

At the **Vegetable Oil Company**, physical hazards were prominent, with 75% of workers reporting exposure to noise and 68.3% to heavy lifting. Chemical hazards were also prevalent, with 89.7% noting exposure and 48.3% experiencing chemical splashes. Biological hazards were reported by 42.5%, mainly due to poor waste disposal practices. Psychosocial risks, especially due to prolonged work hours and inadequate breaks, were significant. At **Factory B** chemical hazards were the most commonly identified risks, with 88% of workers

acknowledging exposure. Psychological hazards were also prevalent, with 60% reporting stress-related issues. However, specific data on physical and biological hazards were not detailed in the study. Nonetheless, the presence of firefighting systems in 90% of plants shows preparedness for fire-related risks. Overall, both factories face considerable hazard exposure, but **Factory B** appears to be better equipped to respond to them.

Discussion, Conclusion, and Recommendations

DISCUSSION

This study revealed significant occupational hazards among workers in two selected industries in Abia State, Nigeria—chemical, physical, biological, and psychosocial. Chemical exposure was predominant, with 89.7% and 88% of workers in the vegetable oil company and Factory B, respectively, reporting such risks. These findings align with Abdulsalam *et al.* (2024) and Adejumo *et al.* (2023), who similarly reported high levels of chemical exposure among Nigerian industrial workers, often due to inadequate protective equipment and insufficient training.

Physical hazards such as noise (75%) and heavy lifting (68.3%) were common at the vegetable oil company, corroborating Ezenwaji *et al.* (2018), who identified similar exposures in sawmill environments. However, Factory B lacked specific data on physical hazards despite its stronger structural safety systems, including emergency plans (80%) and firefighting equipment (90%), partially meeting OSHA-recommended standards (OSHA, 2023).

Psychosocial risks, including long work hours and stress, were reported by 68.9% of respondents in the vegetable oil company and 60% in Factory B. These mirror Saeed *et al.* (2021) and WHO (2023a) findings, which highlight psychosocial stress as an emerging concern in occupational health. Notably, while hazard awareness was high across both sites, safety training and management commitment were inadequate, echoing ILO (2023) and Olatunji (2018), who emphasized the need for integrated safety systems supported by leadership and worker participation.

Despite Factory B's relative infrastructure advantage, both settings lacked regular safety reviews, structured training, and medical surveillance—gaps also noted by Enwere *et al.* (2024). Biological hazards were underrecognized, suggesting a broader pattern of neglect in non-health sectors (WHO, 2023b).

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that occupational hazards—both physical and chemical—are prominent in the vegetable oil processing sector, with relatively higher control measures observed in the Factory B. However, gaps in waste disposal, training, psychosocial health management, and surveillance persist in both locations. A comprehensive approach that includes both engineering controls and behavioral interventions is required to address these deficiencies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Strengthen enforcement of occupational health policies and regulatory compliance across all industrial sectors.
2. Institutionalize regular safety training and awareness programs targeting both management and workers.
3. Implement medical surveillance and periodic health checks to monitor the effects of chemical and physical exposures.
4. Improve waste management infrastructure and enforce safe disposal practices.
5. Integrate psychosocial risk assessments into workplace safety planning, including shift restructuring and counseling services.

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REFERENCES

1. Abdulsalam, A., Aliyu, M., Umar, L., & Olayemi, M. (2024). Knowledge and practices toward occupational safety among workers in vibrated block industries: A cross-sectional study. *Caliphate Journal of Health Sciences*. <https://c-jhs.com/knowledge-and-practices-toward-occupational-safety-among-workers-in-vibrated-block-industries-a-cross-sectional-study/>
2. Adejumo, O. E., Ojo, O. A., & Adejumo, A. A. Occupational exposures and associated health outcomes among Nigerian workers. *Journal of Public Health in Africa*, 2023; 14(1). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9972440/>
3. Enwere, O. O., Opara, I. M., & Chima, U. N. Occupational health hazards among workers in manufacturing industries in Nigeria: A review. *Scientific African*, 2023; 21: e01631. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2468227624000759>
4. Ezenwaji, I. O., Enwere, O. O., & Nnebue, C. C. Patterns and predictors of occupational injuries among sawmill workers in a South Eastern state of Nigeria. *Open Journal of Safety Science and Technology*, 2018; 8(4): 161–173. <https://www.scirp.org/journal/paperinformation.aspx?paperid=93237>
5. International Labour Organization (ILO). (2023). Safety and health at work. <https://www.ilo.org/topics-and-sectors/safety-and-health-work>
6. Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA). (2023). Recommended practices for safety and health programs. <https://www.osha.gov/safety-management>
7. Olatunji, O. A. Assessment of health and safety practices on job performance of construction workers in South West Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 2018; 8(12): 288–305. <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v8-i12/5016>
8. Saeed, A. A., Mohamed, H. K., & Elsabagh, H. M. Occupational stress among industrial workers: Prevalence and associated factors. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 2021; 18(10): 5423. <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/18/10/5423>
9. World Health Organization (WHO). (2023a). Occupational health. <https://www.who.int/health-topics/occupational-health>

10. World Health Organization (WHO). (2023b). Occupational hazards in the health sector: Hazard identification tool. <https://www.who.int/tools/occupational-hazards-in-health-sector>